

THE HITHERTO UNREVEALED ASTRONOMICAL SECRETS OF THE UNIVERSE

WHERE ARE THE PARADISE AND THE HEAVENS?

— THEY ARE THE STARS AND PLANETS SITUATED ABOVE THE FIRMAMENT, AND FURTHER BEYOND THE ABOVE UNIVERSAL SEA.

The mathematical evaluation with calculations is the base and root of Astronomy.

[For all the branches of science, Mathematics is the base, and so Mathematics is, in fact, the root of all the branches of wisdom].

The creation and setting of the universe are in the divisions of $\frac{2}{3}$ and $\frac{1}{3}$ as double and half. Firstly the creation of the very far-away unapproachable area of the universe is based on $\frac{2}{3}$, and the creation of the approachable area as the Visible universe is based on $\frac{2}{9}$. Here, $\frac{1}{3}$ is divided into $\frac{2}{9}$ and $\frac{1}{9}$, while $\frac{2}{9}$ is the inhabited area in the Visible universe and the remaining $\frac{1}{9}$ area is the uninhabitable Underworld area with many divisions, but finally, this $\frac{1}{9}$ area is totally turned into the lake of fire. When we say about **the creation out of 9**, the two major divisions are $\frac{6}{9}$ unapproachable area and $\frac{2}{9}$ approachable area, which includes $\frac{2}{81}$ area of Dry land. But that Dry land is down from the firmament which is under the sky. That is while the very major portion of the approachable area is above the firmament and above the sky.

Astronomical calculation begins with Digit 9. In the first creation, there was created the unapproachable area that exists in the $\frac{6}{9}$ area of the entire universe. Again the $\frac{6}{9}$ area of the unapproachable area is divided into 3 Regions as Northern Region or the Highest Region in the $\frac{2}{9}$ area, the Western Region or Starry Region in the $\frac{2}{9}$ area, and the Eastern Region or Cloudy Region in the $\frac{2}{9}$ area ($\frac{2}{9} + \frac{2}{9} + \frac{2}{9} = \frac{6}{9} =$ the total unapproachable area).

Each of these Regions is divided into 4 Zones totalling 12 Zones for the three Regions. Each Zone has 8 Circuits of stars and so for the 12 Zones there are $12 \times 8 = 96$ Circuits of stars.

Each Region has a Capital Mount, which has 4 Circuits of stars making 12 Circuits of stars for the 3 Capital Mounts of the 3 Regions. So the total Circuits of stars in the unapproachable area is $96 + 12 = 108$ Circuits of stars.

Secondly, there was the creation of the $\frac{2}{9}$ approachable area of the universe as the Southern Region. There is a fascinating aspect that in between the unapproachable area and the approachable area, there is the Eastern Vacuum Gulf in the $\frac{2}{81}$ area, below which there was the creation of one Region as the Southern Region comprising the Second Heavens and the First Heavens. The Second Heavens is in the $\frac{12}{81}$ area and the First Heavens is in the $\frac{4}{81}$ area. Moreover, in the First Heavens, there is the rainbow-coloured Universal Sea in the below half part of the First Heavens as the Above Universal Sea, which has the Soul Bank of the pre-existent souls, and just above that there is situated the Paradise as an Island. This Above Universal Sea has rainbow-coloured waters in the seven colours of Violet, Indigo, Blue, Green, Yellow, Orange and Red, and the acronym is VIBGYOR.

There are 4 Zones totally for the Southern Region. Unlike the Zone in the unapproachable area, here each Zone in the approachable area has 9 Circuits of stars, making an equal number of 36 Circuits of Stars for the Southern Region. Rather, there is the $\frac{2}{81}$ Dry land area underneath the Southern Region, and that Dry land area consists of the area down from the Midair to the earth.

Thirdly and finally, there is the creation of the Underworld in the $\frac{9}{81}$ area, which comprises different divisions. This will be finally converted and created as the lake of fire in the $\frac{1}{9}$ area.

Thus, in brief, the total heavens (the unapproachable area, which is the Third Heavens, and the approachable inhabited area which is the Second Heavens and the First Heavens together) have the total of 144 Circuits of stars ($108 + 36 = 144$).

The stars of the Third Heavens are more bright and bigger compared to the stars of the Second Heavens and of the First Heavens, which are less bright and smaller in size. Compared to the stars in the areas of the heavens in 144 Circuits of stars, the dullest and the smallest stars are for the area of the Dry land, of which the lowest part is the Earthsphere, and the last planet of that Earthsphere is our planet earth.

THE BRIGHT AND LUMINOUS-LOOKING AREAS ARE ABOVE THE SKY THAT IS ABOVE THE FIRMAMENT.

This above area is in four Regions and 16 Zones. This above area itself is in two divisions of unapproachable top area and the approachable below area at present. The unapproachable area itself is in three Regions and in twelve Zones and in three Capital Mountains, while the approachable area is one Region with four Zones but without the Capital Mount for this Region. The total area above the sky that is above the firmament is in 144 Circuits of bright and luminous stars with brightly seen areas of luminosity.

There is another lower grade four Circuits of stars down from the firmament or down from the Midair. This area is known as the Dry land with the sky and the earth. Really, the areas above the firmament are unshakable and permanent forever and ever. But the Dry land area down from the Midair that is down from the firmament till the earth is the shakable

and movable part of the universe, and that shaking with moving will take place in due time. When astronomically we look into the areas of the Dry land, there will be an end for the Dry land area without a distant time. So, the four Circuits of stars of the Dry land are with many galaxies of stars being movable and shakable, and in the future there will be the disappearance of them, and so from then, there will be replaced a vast vacuum area down from the Midair as the Big Southern Vacuum.

THE FIRSTLY, THE SECONDLY AND THE THIRDLY CREATED AREAS ARE TOGETHER THE PRESENT UNIVERSE.

The firstly created area

The $\frac{6}{9}$ unapproachable area being with the $\frac{2}{81}$ area of Eastern Vacuum Gulf underneath it was the firstly created part of the universe.

The secondly created area

The $\frac{2}{9}$ approachable area of bright and luminous stars being further with $\frac{2}{81}$ Dry land area underneath the firmament being with the diagonally lying $\frac{1}{567}$ area of Southern Vacuum Gulf at its bottom altogether was the secondly created part of the universe.

The thirdly created area

Finally the $\frac{9}{81}$ area of the uninhabitable Underworld was the thirdly created part of the universe which was created almost together with the recreation of the Earthsphere. Thus, here the astrology is negatively lying in connection with both the nearby stars, which are with their sweet influence on us in connection with the Underworld and the Underworld areas.

The divisions of the Underworld are only after its creation.

(i) $\frac{1}{81}$ area of Darkened Hell

(ii) $\frac{1}{567}$ area of Lowest Hell, the Flame

(iii) $\frac{2}{81}$ area of the Below Universal Sea with the terribly seen dark waters

(iv) $\frac{6}{81}$ area of Bottomless Pit with Tartarus in it.

The already existing divisions of the Dry land area

- (i) **Midair** area as the firmament with the physical constitution of silver having the area of 4 Circuits of stars
- (ii) Below the above-said area, there is an unequal Circuit of stars with 70 Chains of stars whose above division is **Cloudsphere** with the physical constitution of brass having 30 Chains of stars.
- (iii) The next 40 Chains of stars are together the **Zodiac**, which is with the equal space area of the Cloudsphere, but with the physical constitution of iron.
- (iv) The **Earthsphere** which is alone the six yoms' (six days') Recreated area with the physical constitution of iron mixed with clay. This Earthsphere consists of several stars, including the Bear (*Saptharshi*).

Our Solar system with the planet earth is here even with the same planets with the same planet life of the earth, both in the Solar system and in the planets of the remaining star systems of this Earthsphere. But the present atmospheric life of the earth is only for mankind and for the animal world for them to live with the same breath of life from the atmospheric life.

THE SIMILAR ASTRONOMICAL DIVISIONS OF THE UNIVERSE

There is a unique astronomical theory that there are four equal parts and a fifth unequal part in the segmentation of the universe.

So, in the first segmentation of the universe, there are four equal Regions and an unequal Underworld area as half of a Region as:

$$\frac{2}{9} + \frac{2}{9} + \frac{2}{9} + \frac{2}{9} \text{ ———— } + \frac{1}{9} = \frac{9}{9}$$

Each Region has four equal Zones and an unequal area of Capital Mountain of stars as:

$$\frac{4}{81} + \frac{4}{81} + \frac{4}{81} + \frac{4}{81} \text{ ———— } + \frac{2}{81} = \frac{18}{81} \left[\frac{2}{9} \right]$$

The four Regions are the Northern Region at first, the Western Region secondly, the Eastern Region thirdly, and the Southern Region fourthly, which is our Region.

Among the four Regions, our Southern Region is still unequal against the Northern, Western, and Eastern Regions above, where each Zone is with eight Circuits of stars and an unequal area of Capital Mountain of stars having four Circuits of stars, totalling 36 Circuits of stars in one of those Regions as:

$$\mathbf{8 \times 4 = 32 + 4 = 36 \text{ Circuits of stars.}}$$

So in the Northern Region, there are 32 Circuits of stars throughout in four Zones + four Circuits of stars in the Capital Mountain area, together totalling 36 Circuits of stars.

Equal to this, in the Western Region there are 36 Circuits of stars

and equal to these, in the Eastern Region there are 36 Circuits of stars.

Instead of the area of three capital mountains of stars in the unapproachable area, there is the area of Midair at the bottom of the Southern Region.

This area of Midair is with four Circuits of stars and with an unequal Circuit of stars, which is the only unequal Circuit of stars in the universe. So in the Southern Region itself, there are 40 Circuits of stars and an unequal Circuit of stars as **9 x 4 = 36 + 4 + 1 unequal Circuit of stars with 70 Chains of stars.**

[9 Circuits of stars x 4 Zones = 36 Circuits of stars + 4 Midair Circuits of stars + 1 unequal Circuit of stars]

So, now totally there are 148 Circuits of stars and an unequal Circuit of stars in the total universe, besides *the area of the Underworld, where there are* neither systematic Circuits of stars nor Cosmic light as the life-giving factor of the stars.

The Midair closer to us

The four Circuits of stars in the Midair are Arcturus, Pleiades, Orion, and Mazzaroth.

Below these four Midair Circuits, there is unequally a fifth Circuit of stars with 70 Chains of stars as the only unequal Circuit of stars in the universe which is our Circuit of stars, and is mainly in two divisions.

1. The Cloudsphere with 30 Chains of stars
2. The Zodiac with 40 Chains of stars in the equal space of the Cloudsphere

Because of the lesser area, the stars in the Zodiac are smaller in size, and of course, lesser in brightness.

Thus, it is clear that the Zodiac is unequal in the universe with 40 Chains of stars in the equal area of 30 Chains of stars in the Cloudsphere. Again, our

Circuit of stars is unequal as the only fifth Circuit of stars in the limited area. Again, our Southern Zone in the Southern Region is unequal with watery area and also such atmosphere there, and also with the Above Universal Sea. And again, our Southern Region as the fourth Region in the universe itself is unequal compared to the other three Regions in the universe. But one special feature is that all four Regions are habitable areas, and almost all Zones in the Southern Region are already inhabited by the good angels in the areas above the Universal Sea and by the fallen angels, mainly in the firmament areas, further by the Aliens in our nearby areas and mankind inhabit only the earth.

THE 14-FOLD VACUUM AREA AROUND AND THE TWO VACUUM GULFS WITHIN THE PHYSICAL UNIVERSE OF MATTER

The acuteness of dissimilarity is projected through the 14-fold vacuum area around and is projected in the universe with two Vacuum Gulfs in between the unequal areas. So between the total three Regions above and the Southern Region, there is the Eastern Vacuum Gulf in $\frac{2}{81}$ area. This in-between Vacuum Gulf is the still remaining Vacuum area without any qualities of the Physical universe of matter in this in-between Vacuum Gulf area which is in $\frac{2}{81}$ area of the universe.

Again, at the bottom of the Southern Region, there is the Southern Vacuum Gulf in $\frac{1}{567}$ area, set diagonally to separate the Underworld from us.

Apart from these two Vacuum Gulfs in the in-between areas, there is the largest vacuum in circular shape and in 14-fold area around the Physical universe of matter which is in elliptical shape. From this largest vacuum around, through the gravitational force the Physical universe of matter is hung, and in such a largest vacuum around, the Physical universe of matter rotates and runs throughout.

The unequal Underworld area as half of a Region

At sundry times and in diverse manners, the creation of the universe is fulfilled in its final state, so to say, very recently the Underworld is separated in $\frac{9}{81}$

area under the diagonally set Vacuum Gulf that is underneath the Southern Vacuum Gulf.

The top area of the Underworld — $\frac{1}{81}$ area of Darkened Hell

The middle area of the Underworld — $\frac{2}{81}$ area of Below Universal Sea of thick dark waters

Above this Below Universal Sea of thick dark waters, there is $\frac{1}{567}$ area of an island as the area of Flame, which is the Lowest Hell.

The bottom part of the Underworld — $\frac{6}{81}$ area underneath, which still remains as the Bottomless Pit as the Tartarus

Origin of the universe, which gives us the Astronomical evaluation

Though the Cause of the creation of the universe is the Great Creation Power from the never-ending past ages with the triangular motion of Omnipotence for creation, Omniscience for creation and Omnipresence for creation causing Infinity, the root Medium of creation is the having progressed seven ratios of darkneses of the Infinity whereas the setting of the Vacuum Universe circularly was through the circular spreading of light against the darkness. But after crore x crore years (after Alpha years) the Great Creation Energy passed through the Space, that is, passed through the ideological waves that had already been filled up in the Space audibly, visibly, and tangibly, where the Matter creation came into being 360 crore years ago, which became a proper Matter universe in elliptical shape with the rotation and revolution collectively as well as with the rotation and revolution of each star and each planet from 344 crore years ago, which is the present Matter universe.

Doxology

*Through your reading of the above-seen ten pages of ‘**The Entirely New Astronomy to the world**’ we hope that you have seen astronomically the Heavens in this paper. Can you reach there by travelling throughout your lifespan at light years’ speed because you have to cross a minimum of ten thousand crores of galaxies, each galaxy being with more than ten thousand crores of stars? If you cannot approach the First Heavens at that level, how far are the Second Heavens, and then how much more distant are the Third Heavens?*

Please realise now that the Heavens are not the imaginary place, but the Heavens are lying distantly in the more areas of the universe that are with good looks and with good luminosity. Mankind is now limited with this tiny Solar system, which also is difficult for them in their reach and comprehension. But the Author can lead you to those Heavenly places now astronomically, and further literally in the near future. The Heavens are unobservable areas for the present astronomers.

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**Mr. Abraham M. T.
(known as the Man of the East)
Superscientist of the astronomical secrets,
who represents India and Israel**

Promoters of Superscience

83, Church hill lane, Ooty - 643001, The Nilgiris, Tamil Nadu, India. Mob: +91-9899043585
Email: <superscience.promo@gmail.com; superiorwisdom1@superscienceinfo.com>
www.superscienceinfo.com